

Walking Through the Hebrew Berlin: A Spatial Analysis of the City's Representations in Modern Hebrew Literature

Abstract

Berlin, the capital of modern Germany, was the most significant center of German Jews from the end of the 19th century until the second world war. As such, the city became a significant center of Hebrew literature, and more generally of what can be called Hebrew modernism – a process culminating, in some ways, during the Weimar Republic, at times of growing tensions between cosmopolitanism and the rise of anti-Semitism. This situation complicates the ways in which the city (as well as the German culture it symbolized) is perceived in Jewish writings. This complexity was also expressed in the city's fictional representations in Hebrew literature of the twentieth and twenty-first centuries.

In this short paper I will take on a spatial point of view, examining two Hebrew novels that deal with this tension: *Avedot* (Losses) by Lea Goldberg (2010 [193?]), and *Lifney Hamakom* (Upon a Certain Place) by Haim Be'er (2007). *Avedot*, found in Goldberg's archive and probably written in the 1930's, was not published during its author's lifetime. Its plot takes place between 1932-1933, when the novel's protagonist, the Hebrew poet Elhanan Kron, travels from Palestine to Berlin to complete a scientific research he took on himself. Interestingly, *Lifney Hamakom* also tells a story of a writer the protagonist Haim Be'er (who shares his name with the actual author), a frustrated author who cannot finish his novel. Zussman, a well successful realtor, invites him to Berlin to join a group of Israeli and German intellectuals, whose purpose is to determine the topic for a seminar that commemorates Zussman's late daughter Miriam.

The plots in both these novels sketch two multidimensional maps of Berlin. Despite their obvious connection to modernist novels of the Flâneur such as *Berlin, Alexanderplatz* by Alfred Döblin (1929), the maps that emerge from these Hebrew novels have entirely different literary-spatial characteristics: While modernist urban novels tend to be led by spatial logic, leading the reader through the city's maze, and creating a synchronized sense of the city, these two novels tend to be rather selective in their sightseeing. *Avedot*, for example, focuses merely on the city center and precisely on its academic institutions; *Lifney Hamkom* is even more selective: its

protagonists rarely visit sights that do not have historical significance for Jewish history or for the memory of the Holocaust. The selective nature of these two maps does not allow the reader to experience the city like in the typical urban novel, but instead, it makes him or her question the symbolic nature of the relatively few chosen sights.

In order to construct and then to analyze these maps, I annotated the sights in each novel using the computer-assisted markup tool CATMA (catma.de); then, I exported them and represented them as a layer on a digital map of the city (based on the Google maps platform). In addition, I added what can be called 'literary metadata' for each sight, classifying them by their characteristics as shaped in the novels (for example, academic institutions, historical sights, memorials, cafés), as well as by the way in which they function in the plot (for example, sights connected to questions of Germans-Jews relations, Jewish history, liberal identity, etc.). The combination of spatial data and literary insights enriched the map: An integration of close and distant reading (the latter is seen in the act of mapping) enables me to understand the sites and the routes between them, actual (as existing on the map) as well as symbolic (unveiled by the process of interpretation).

Using this methodology, I will show how the tension between cosmopolitan Berlin and its fascist history shapes the fictional maps outlined by these novels. Moreover, I will conceptualize the different roles of the two narrators as tour guides: The first asking to maintain a "frozen" image of the beloved city, representing the desired European culture while seemingly depicting a literary farewell postcard from it; the second emphasizing dimensions of a 'vertical' historical memory that arises in the face of the 'horizontal' encounter with the city's sites.